

CODE MIXING ANALYSIS IN *DIVORTIARE* NOVEL

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Abstract

This research aimed to analyze the usage of code mixing in *Divortiare* novel that was written by Ika Natasssa. The objective of this research is to find out the type of code mixing that is used in *Divortiare* Novel. This study is a qualitative research. The technique of collecting data was done by using documentary technique. The odd number chapters in *Divortiare* novel are used as the data of this study. The data were analyzed by using Miles and Hubberman model. The findings of this study show that there are three types of code mixing used namely: insertion, congruent lexicalization and alternation. The result of this study showed that insertion was used 71,75%; congruent lexicalization was used 21,08% and alternation was used 7,17%. Based on the result of this study, it shows that the most dominant type of code mixing used in *Divortiare* novel is insertion. So, it can be concluded that the writer of the novel use insertion most dominantly cause discuss about particular topic, being emphatic about something and expressing group identity.

Keywords: Code Mixing, Novel, Types of Code Mixing.

1. INTRODUCTION

Novel is a form of literary works that are most popular in the world. In understanding novel, it is needed to know the linguistic forms that used in that novel. Linguistic form used in novel will influence the readers to read the novels. This literary linguistic form most widely circulated due to the extensive communication resources in society. Novel can be used as a good read for self perfection. A good novel is a novel which has contents that can

humanize the readers. The writers of novel try to entertain the readers in reading the novel by using the good language. In writing the idea in the novel some of the writers used code mixing in order to entertain the readers. Code mixing and code switching often occur in various existing community conversation in the world. Utterances in novel can be analyzed to see how the language used in that novel.

Code mixing can be found in spoken and written languages. On the other hand, code mixing also can be found in magazine, newspaper, book, novel, etc. Muysken (2000: 1) states that code mixing is the use of lexical items and grammatical features between two languages that appear in one sentence. The focus of this research is to analyze the types of code mixing in *Divortiare* novel. The problems of the study of this research are: 1) what are the types of code mixing used in *Divortiare* novel? 2) what is the most dominant type of code mixing used in *Divortiare* novel? 3) what are the reasons of the most dominant type of code mixing used in *Divortiare* novel? Meanwhile, the objectives of the study are: 1) finding out the types of code mixing used in *Divortiare* novel ; 2) finding out the most dominant type of code mixing used in *Divortiare* novel; 3) finding out the reasons of the most dominant type of code mixing used in *Divortiare* novel.

Based on the explanation previously, the researchers interested in analyzing the using of code mixing by the writer of the *Divortiare* novel in expressing the feelings, ideas and opinion. This study is expected to be useful in sociolinguistics studies and language use in community communication.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This research used Muysken theory (2000) in analyzing the types of code mixing that are used in *Divortiare* novel. Muysken (2000:76) states that the term of code mixing refers to all

cases where lexical items and grammatical features from two languages appear in one sentence. On the other hand, code mixing refers to the mixing of two or more languages or language varieties in speech. Some examples of code mixing used in conversation between Indonesia – English.

A: *Hari ini don't forget come to my party ya.*

B: *Well, I will go tapi kalau gue nggak sibuk ya.*

Muysken (2000: 60) states there are three types of code mixing, namely: insertion, alternation, and congruent lexicalization. Insertion is code mixing used in sentences by inserted the constituent in the sentences. For example, '*hari ini kamu melihatannya sweet seperti gula*'. Alternation is code mixing used in sentences that used two languages present in clause and separated. For example, '*dia tidak bisa berbicara and cannot say anything forever*'. Congruent lexicalization is seeing to more likely when two languages are typologically similar when the word order of the sentence is same. For example, '*kita always melakukan yang terbaik but kendala selalu datang*'.

Hoffman (1991) states that there are seven points reason in using code mixing as follows: 1) Talking about a particular topic. People sometimes prefer to talk about a particular topic in one language rather than in another language. 2) Quoting somebody else. People sometimes like to quote a famous expression or saying of some

well known figures. 3) Being emphatic about something. 4) Interjection. Code mixing used among bilingual or multilingual people sometimes mark interjection or sentence connectors. It may happen unintentionally or intentionally. 5) Repetition used for clarification. When a bilingual wants to clarify his/her speech in order to be understood more by the listener, the speaker sometimes use both of the language that the speaker masters saying the same utterance. 6) Intention of clarifying the speech content for interlocutor. When a bilingual person talks to another bilingual, it was mentioned that there will be lots of code switching and code mixing that occur. 7) Expressing group identity. Code mixing can also be used to express group identity.

3. RESEARCH METHOD

This research was conducted by using qualitative method. Creswell (2013: 62) states that qualitative research is an inquiry approach useful for exploring and understanding a central phenomenon. The source data of this research is *Divortiare* novel. The data were collected by using reading technique. There are eleven chapters analyzed in this research. This research use interactive data analysis that was proposed by Miles, Hubberman & Saldana (2014: 10) that is shown in the Figure 1. The data collection in this study was done by using documentary technique, then reducing the data, after that display the data and come to the conclusion.

Figure 1
Interactive Data Analysis (Miles, Hubberman & Saldana, 2014: 10)

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Having analyzed the data from *Divortiare* novel, it was found that the three types of code mixing were used in

this novel. The result of the using of code mixing in *Divortiare* novel is shown in the following table.

Table 1
Occurrences of Types of Code Mixing in *Divortiare* novel

No.	Data	Types of Code Mixing			Total
		Insertion	Alternation	Congruent Lexicalization	
1.	Data 1	4	0	1	5
2.	Data 2	19	5	8	32
3.	Data 3	28	2	8	38
4.	Data 4	9	4	3	16
5.	Data 5	23	1	3	27
6.	Data 6	16	2	5	23
7.	Data 7	3	0	0	3
8.	Data 8	10	0	3	13
9.	Data 9	10	0	5	15
10.	Data 10	27	1	6	34
11.	Data 11	11	1	5	17
Total					223

From Table 1 show that there are 223 of code mixing used in *Divortiare* novel. Furthermore, it is also shows that the occurrences of the using of code mixing in each data is different each other. It means that, the writer of *Divortiare* novel used types of code mixing in each chapter differently in order to give an interesting point to the reader in reading the novel. There are

some data from Table 1 that is not found the using of types of code mixing (data 1, data 7, data 8 and data 9). Meanwhile, there are also some data that used the three types of code mixing (data 2, data 3, data 4, data 5, data 6, data 10 and data 11). In classifying the most dominant types of code mixing that are used in *Divortiare* novel shown in Table 2 below.

Table 2
Percentage of Types of Code Mixing in *Divortiare* Novel

No.	Types of Code Mixing	Total	Percentage
1.	Insertion	160	71,75 %
2.	Alternation	16	7,17%
3.	Congruent Lexicalization	47	21,08%
		223	100%

Based on Table 2, it is shown that from the three types of code mixing used in *Divortiare* novel, insertion is most dominantly used which has 71,75% followed by congruent lexicalization which has 21,08% and alternation which has 7,17%. The

example of the using of types of code mixing in *Divortiare* novel can be seen as follows.

4.1 Insertion Types of Code Mixing

Insertion is the lexical item or constituent from one language takes

place of a comparable item in the other language but it is inserted into the structure of the other language. Muysken (2000: 60) states that insertion tends to be content word, nested, selected element and single constituent. Some examples of insertion types of code mixing in *Divortiare* novel are presented as follows.

- 1) *Jika kita pintar menggunakan seluruh sense yang kita miliki, kita akan belajar banyak dari seseorang hanya dari percakapan dua menit.* (Data 1)

Sense shows that it consists of word, because the use of **sense** which has the translation in Indonesia 'rasa' is categorized as content word as noun. This code mixing has followed the rules type of insertion.

- 2) *Maksud kamu apa bilang aku intercranial bleeding?* (Data 2)

Intercranial bleeding shows that it consists of phrases because the use of **intercranial bleeding** which has the translation in Indonesia 'pendarahan intrakranial' is categorized as nested. This code mixing has followed the rules type of insertion.

- 3) *Tapi bukan berarti saking extrovertnya, kalau ke belakang aku harus ditemani orang ya, hehehe.* (Data 5)

Extrovert shows it consists of word, because the use of **extrovert** which has the translation in Indonesia 'percaya diri' is categorized as content word as noun. This code mixing has followed the rules type of insertion.

- 4) *Jadi waktu itu ceritanya, aku dan teman-teman lagi nyoba surfing.* (Data 7)

Surfing shows that it consists of word because the use of surfing which has the translation in Indonesia 'berselancar' is categorized as content word as noun. This code mixing has followed the rules type of insertion.

- 5) *Tidak ingat kapan terakhir kali aku dating.* (Data 11)

Dating shows that it consists of phrases because the use of **dating** which has the translation in Indonesia 'kencan' is categorized content word as noun. This code mixing has followed the rules type of insertion.

4.2 Alternation Types of Code Mixing

In alternation type, languages occur alternately each with their structure. It is indicated that halfway code mixing through the sentence and one language is replaced by the other. Alternation divided into three namely: several constituent, doubling, and self correction. Some examples of alternation types of code mixing in *Divortiare* novel are presented as follows.

- 1) *Rasanya kepalaku mau pecah saat aku membuka mata dan I'm in a hospital.* (Data 3)

I'm in a hospital is independent clause because the use of **I'm in a hospital** which has the translation in Indonesia 'saya berada di rumah sakit' is categorized as several constituent. This code mixing has

followed the rules type of alternation.

- 2) **You know**, *terakhir kali aku ke Bali tahun lalu, aku disengat ubur-ubur.* (Data 7)

You know is dependent clause because the uses of **you know** which has the translation in Indonesia '*kamu tahu*' is categorized as several constituent in alternation type. This code mixing has followed the rules type of alternation.

- 3) **I know**, *ia mengangguk lagi.* (Data 7)

I know is dependent clause because the use of **I know** which has the translation in Indonesia '*saya tahu*' is categorized as several constituent. This code mixing has followed the rules type of alternation.

- 4) *Yang jelas sejak itu aku makin yakin keluar rumah emang enggak boleh mati gaya, you never know who you're gonna run into.* (Data 9)

You never know who you're gonna run into is independent clause because the use of **you never know who you're gonna run into** which has the translation in Indonesia '*anda tidak pernah tahu siapa yang akan anda hadapi*' is categorized as several constituent. This code mixing has followed the rules type of alternation.

- 5) **I know that was supposed to be a compliment**, *tapi yang ada di pikiranku hanya pertanyaan siapa perempuan itu.* (Data 11)

I know that was supposed to be a compliment is dependent clause because the use of **I know that was supposed to be a compliment** which has the translation in Indonesia '*aku tahu itu seharusnya menjadi pujian*' is categorized as several constituent. This code mixing has followed the rules type of alternation.

4.3 Congruent Lexicalization Types of Code Mixing

In congruent lexicalization types, the grammatical structure is shared by languages A and B, then words from both languages A and B are inserted or less randomly. The congruent lexicalization is characterized by function words, homophonous, linear equivalent, and mixed collocation. Some examples of congruent lexicalization types of code mixing in *Divortiare* novel are presented as follows.

- 1) *Puluhan menit yang saya lalui di airport lounge menunggu pesawat take off.* (Data 1)

Airport lounge and **take off** are categorized as function word in alternation type. It is because both phrases contribute to the grammatical structure of the sentence. This code mixing has followed the rules type of congruent lexicalization.

- 2) *"Hahaha, puas banget", ujar Wina sambil menyodorkan satu bucket kecil es krim Ben and Jerry.* (Data 3)

Bucket, and are categorized as congruent lexicalization because

both of words are categorized as function words. The two words contribute to the grammatical structure of sentence. This code mixing has followed the rules type of congruent lexicalization.

- 3) *Masa relationship manager tidak bisa memmanage relationshipnya sendiri.* (Data 5)

Relationship manager and **manage relationship** are categorized as congruent lexicalization because both of words are categorized as function words. The two words contribute to the grammatical structure of sentence. This code mixing has followed the rules type of congruent lexicalization.

- 4) *Tumpukan folder di mejaku hari ini udah ngalah-ngalahin tumpukan textbook zaman kuliah dulu.* (Data 7)

Folder and **textbook** are categorized as congruent lexicalization because both of words are categorized as function words. The two words contribute to the grammatical structure of sentence. This code mixing has followed the rules type of congruent lexicalization.

- 5) *Aku mengangguk, memasukkan pakaian gantiku ke travelling bag, penyakit last-minute packing yang nggak sembuh-sembuh dari dulu.* (Data 15)

Travelling bag and **last minute packing** are categorized as congruent lexicalization because both of words are categorized as function words. The two words

contribute to the grammatical structure of sentence. This code mixing has followed the rules type of congruent lexicalization.

There are some reasons of the using insertion the most dominantly used in *Divortiare* novel, they are:

- a) Talking about a particular topic. In *Divortiare* novel, they type of code mixing most dominantly used is insertion. As it is known that insertion is lexical items or constituents of a single language occur on comparable items in other languages but are inserted into other language structure. *Divortiare* novel contains many insertion type of code mixing because many words are related to English languages in each topic or chapter and also it is found that the main reason of the most dominant type of code mixing in *Divortiare* novel is talk about a particular topic.
- b) Being emphatic about something. As it is known that some who is talking by using a language that is not his native language wants to be emphatic about something. Intentionally or unintentionally will mix with other languages.
- c) Expressing group identity. Code mixing can also be used to express group identity. The way of communication of novelist groups are obviously different from the other groups. On the other hand, the way of communication of one community is different from the people who are out of the community.

5. CONCLUSION

After analyzing all the data, some conclusions are drawn as follows: 1) 223 of code mixing were used in *Divortiare* novel which is divided into three types namely: insertion which consists of 160 codes mixing; alternation which consists of 16 codes mixing and congruent lexicalization which consists of 47 codes mixing; 2) from the three types of code mixing found in *Divortiare* novel, insertion type of code mixing is dominantly used which has the percentage 71,75%; 3) the reason of insertion is dominantly used in *Divortiare* novel cause it dominates talking a particular topic, emphatic something and expresses group identity. This study hopes gives useful advantages for the novel writer in using code mixing in their novels in the future. It is concluded that in *Divortiare* novel the three types of code mixing that proposed by Muysken (2000) are used in delivered the message in entertaining the readers. Meanwhile, from seven points of reason of using code mixing (Hoffman, 1991) only three points found in reasoning the use of code mixing in *Divortiare* novel.

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